

GRAMMATICAL COMPETENCE

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Abstract: *This article considers about the innovative methods of teaching grammar at the educational establishments. We tried to analyze and generalize the scholars' approaches towards the problem searched in our article. We hope this work can serve as a manual for teaches while teaching grammar.*

Keywords: *teaching grammar, different approaches, implicit teaching, explicit teaching, pronunciation, communicative method*

Teaching grammar plays a central role in every ESL teacher's classroom. The important question that needs to be answered is: how do I teach grammar? In other words, how do I help students learn the grammar they need. This question is deceptively easy. At first look, you might think that teaching grammar is just a matter of explaining grammar rules to students. However, teaching grammar effectively is a much more complicated matter. Nowadays there is no consensus among educators, psychologists, and trainers about the role of grammar in learning a foreign language. Some authors believe that the formation of grammatical skills is one of the weaknesses in foreign language teaching. Grammar is not trained at school in general; grammar skills are formed on an intuitive, unconscious basis. So, it is "a weak spot" when students use language structures, but do not realize their grammatical information and therefore don't not understand their meaning and can't communicate properly. When learning or using a language, many people find that their grammar is far from perfect. But grammar is inescapable; it is the backbone of any language and must be understood in order for one to communicate effectively. Every time you write something, you are being judged for your grammar, even if it is subconscious. You are less likely to land jobs, you are less likely to get replied to on social media sites, and you are less likely to get contacted when online dating. Having good grammar simply makes you look more intelligent, so it is important for everyone to spend a little time perfecting theirs. We often tell students that the way an individual present himself to the world says a lot about who he is. This is often thought of in terms of address and physical appearance. There are other ways, however, that people send messages about who they are and that is through the way they speak and how they create and share words with others. One reason that it is vital that

an individual learns the correct usages of English grammar is for the impression that it gives others. Failing to use the appropriate English grammar can send the wrong message and can impact the way an individual is perceived by the outside world. That is not to say that those that are learning English or those that struggle with these concepts are not competent, but simply it is saying that to others they may not be perceived as such. This is a sad but true fact regarding the way in which the world perceives each other. It is important to study grammar to speak in a clearer and more effective manner. A person who has unconscious knowledge of grammar may be sufficient for simple language use, but the ones who wish to communicate in an artful manner and well, will seek greater depth of understanding and proficiency that the study of grammar provides.

There is no consensus concerning teaching grammar in ESL. The focus of debate nowadays has shifted to the question of how it can best be taught. Educators continue to search for ways to integrate formal grammar instruction with communicative methods. It seems that the question of whether students should be taught formal grammar in the classroom has neither a generally agreed upon nor a simple answer. One point that most researchers and linguists concur on is that explicit grammatical knowledge does have to be either acquired or learned by second language learners. When teaching grammar in ESL, teachers should demonstrate their willingness to learn from a variety of different viewpoints with regard to the content of grammar instruction as well as the pedagogy of grammar. Grammar teaching in ESL needs to be taught in a manner that is consistent with grammar's new role. The remaining and primary question is, „how-to teach grammar in ESL“ and the challenge lies in discovering effective ways to do this.

REFERENCES:

1. Harmer Jeremy. The Practice of English Language Teaching
2. Махмурян К. С., Лекции по методике преподавания английского языка. Мирлюбов А. А., Обучение проблемы грамматики и фонетики иностранных языков, МИОО, Москва, 2006., 323с
3. Пассов Э. И., Завесова Э. Г., Методы преподавания иностранных языков: «Формирование грамматических навыков» набор руководств, Воронеж № 9. 2002. 156с.